

Computation of Analog Theorems for the Riemann Zeta Function

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Abstract: The Riemann zeta function is the most important special function in the significantly large family of zeta-functions. The Riemann zeta function plays a vital role in the analytic number theory and has applications in applied statistics, physics, and probability theory. This paper presents several analog theorems for the Riemann zeta function.

This paper presents a theorem that related to the harmonic series and the Riemann zeta function.

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1. Introduction

In the earlier days, geometric series [1-16] with positive exponents served as a vital role in the development of differential and integral calculus and also in the summation of series involving the the Riemann zeta function [17, 18]. Geometric series have significant applications in physics, engineering, biology, economics, finance, management, queueing theory, computer science and medicine [19].

2. Harmonic Series and Riemann Zeta Function

The Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s)$ for all complex numbers such as $s = a + ib$ is defined by

$$\zeta(s) = 1^{-s} + 2^{-s} + 3^{-s} + 4^{-s} + 5^{-s} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s}, \quad \forall \Re(s) > 1.$$

Where $\Re(s)$ is the real part of all complex numbers \mathbb{C} such as $s \in \mathbb{C}$.

The harmonic series is an infinite series formed by summing all positive fractions as follows:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} + \dots$$

3. Analog Theorems for Riemann zeta function

Theorem 3.1:
$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n}.$$

Proof. Let us prove this theorem using the geometric series:

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} \right) = \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{6^s} + \dots \right)$$

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^s} + \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{3^s} + \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{4^s} + \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{5^s} + \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{6^s} + \dots$$

Simplifying this equation using the geometric series:

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^s} - 1 \right) + \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{3^s} - 1 \right) + \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{4^s} - 1 \right) + \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{5^s} - 1 \right) + \dots$$

$$\text{Here, } \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^s} - 1 \right) = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{k}} - 1 = \frac{k}{k-1} - 1 = \frac{k-k+1}{k-1} = \frac{1}{k-1} \text{ for } k = 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$$

Now, we conclude that

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n}.$$

The theorem 3.1 provides the relationship between the harmonic series and the Riemann zeta function.

Theorem 3.2: $\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = 1.$

Proof. Let us prove this theorem using the theorem 2.1.

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = \zeta(1) - 1 + \zeta(2) - 1 + \zeta(3) - 1 + \zeta(4) - 1 + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n}$$

$$\zeta(2) - 1 + \zeta(3) - 1 + \zeta(4) - 1 + \zeta(5) - 1 + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n} - \zeta(1) + 1,$$

$$\text{Where } \zeta(1) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^1} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n}.$$

$$\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = 1.$$

Hence proved.

Corollary 3.1: $\sum_{s=3}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = 2 - \frac{\pi^2}{6},$

where the Basel problem indicates that $\zeta(2) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} = \frac{\pi^2}{6}.$

Corollary 3.2: $\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{n^2} + \frac{1}{n^3} + \frac{1}{n^4} + \frac{1}{n^5} + \dots \right) = 1.$

Proof. $\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = \zeta(2) - 1 + \zeta(3) - 1 + \zeta(4) - 1 + \zeta(5) - 1 + \dots = 1$

$$\text{Here, } \zeta(k) - 1 = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^k}.$$

$$\therefore \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{n^2} + \frac{1}{n^3} + \frac{1}{n^4} + \frac{1}{n^5} + \dots \right) = 1.$$

4. Conclusion

In the article, the author has proved several analog theorems for the Riemann zeta function. This idea can enable the scientific researchers for further involvement in research and development.

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